

Interlinked process, product & data quality framework for zero defect manufacturing

D9.3

Data Management Plan update

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ABSTRACT / EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

<p>Abstract</p>	<p>D9.3 "Data Management Plan update," provides a comprehensive overview of the rules and processes implemented during the project's timeline for documenting and protecting project partners information and data sets. In addition, this document includes updated and final tables with the scientific and business data collected and used during the project's lifetime.</p> <p>More specifically, the InterQ Data Management Plan's primary objective is to ensure that the project adheres to legal regulations such as Open Data Access guidelines and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Additionally, it outlines the procedures governing the management of all data generated and collected during project activities. This includes how these research data are employed, preserved, and made accessible for potential re-use.</p> <p>To fulfil the goals of the InterQ project, a plethora of data sets were sourced. They were either originated from business partners, generated during the Pilots, simulated using project modelling capabilities, or collected from external sources. These data sets and information played an important role in designing, testing, and validating the efficacy of InterQ solutions and they are documented in the current updated version of the Data Management Plan.</p> <p>In addition, it should be noted that particular attention was given to comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Data Access Guidelines, which prioritize making project results accessible to fellow researchers and ensuring the sustainable storage of data after project lifetime. For fulling the above-mentioned goals as well as disseminating the project's findings, the project utilized Zenodo and GitLab repositories. These are well established file repositories that are employed to store and share various outputs, including reports, code, data sets, scientific publications and results.</p> <p>Finally, D9.3 serves as a valuable resource for both the research community and industry stakeholders by documenting and in some cases making accessible the outputs generated and/or used during the project's research activities.</p>
<p>Keywords</p>	<p>InterQ, Data Management Plan, Data sharing, Data privacy, GDPR, Data sets, FAIR Management, Open Research Data Pilot</p>

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Microsoft
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PC	Project Coordinator
PST	Project Steering Team
WP	Work Package
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This document was compiled within the context of WP9 “InterQ Project Management” and more specifically within Task 9.3 “Quality, Data, Ethics & Legal issues Management” of the InterQ project. The report is an updated version of D9.2 and it is submitted to the European Commission (EC) as the InterQ's Final Data Management Plan (D9.3). It includes business and scientific data sets collected or produced during the project and defines procedures to be followed to ensure that they are protected, while it shares them publicly so other researchers taking similar endeavours can use or benefit from them.

1.1 Context, Scope and Objectives

A data management plan (DMP) is a document that outlines the procedures and regulations governing data throughout and after project lifetime. It serves the dual purpose of ensuring the effective handling of a project's data sets and results, as well as of identifying and mitigating potential data protection risks. Furthermore, another valuable aspect of a DMP is the definition of clear management rules that facilitates communication and builds trust between project data set providers and the relevant partners that want to use or process them. Ultimately, the advantages of preparing and maintaining a DMP can be summarized as follows:

1. Ensures and demonstrates compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [5] and relevant regulatory obligations.
2. Enhances consortium confidence by facilitating better communication regarding data protection matters.
3. Enables the integration of 'data protection by design' into projects.
4. Fosters knowledge discovery and supports innovation through data and knowledge integration and reuse.
5. Identifies the types of data utilized in the project and establishes methods for safeguarding them.

In this context, InterQ 's initial DMP, submitted at M6 of the project, has already detailed the processes and guidelines followed by project members to ensure compliance with H2020 and EU standards for the handling and processing of research and personal data. This deliverable presents an updated version of the project's initial DMP, with a specific emphasis on documenting the data received, generated, and managed by InterQ project partners during project lifetime as well as any data sets or sources intended to be made publicly available. Lastly, as part of the effort to make research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), this report provides information on:

1. The nature of data collected, processed, and/or generated.
2. Whether data will be shared or made openly accessible.
3. The strategies for curating and preserving data, including post-project preservation measures.

1.2 Relationship to Other Project Outcomes

By maintaining an organized list of data sets, the consortium fosters transparency about the data shared and used among project partners and oversees that their handling followed the applicable project procedures. Additionally, by regularly updating a DMP the project consortium facilitates collaboration among project task leaders by offering a clear overview of available data description, owners, usage and enables different project teams to leverage the shared data sets more efficiently [2].

1.3 Structure of the Document

The current report is organized into five Chapters and two Annexes, as follows:

Chapter 1: Encompasses the introduction of D9.3, which describes the scope and the structure of the document.

Chapter 2: Addresses the requirements outlined by the EC and Horizon 2020 program's official page concerning the necessity for data access throughout the project. Furthermore, it provides a concise overview of the project's data sets' lifecycle and outlines the protocols for handling data to ensure compliance with the FAIR data principles and the GDPR.

Chapter 3: Focuses on InterQ 's file repositories, with particular emphasis on Git repositories and Zenodo. The Git repositories were used by the project for the efficient management and development of project software solutions, while Zenodo was used for disseminating the project's results and data sets.

Chapter 4: Comprises detailed information about InterQ 's data sets per WP, connecting them to the project's objectives and goals.

Chapter 5: Summarizes the conclusions drawn from the report.

2 InterQ Data Management Plan and Open Access Guidelines

This chapter provides a summary of the requirements outlined in the EC Horizon 2020 program's official page applicable to InterQ and all H2020 projects. These requirements pertain to the definitions, management, and safeguarding of scientific, personal, or any other data sets associated with the project, such as:

1. Gathering quantitative and/or qualitative data from the systems of project partners, Pilots deployment, and testing.
2. Collecting data from publicly available sources, including relevant legislation, document databases, government and NGO statistical databases such as OECD¹ and the World Bank etc.
3. Acquiring open-source data from publicly accessible sources.
4. Managing dissemination activities, project workshops, and events, which may include administrative information like participant contact details, communications, questionnaires, interview data, etc.
5. Organizing training, educational programs, and capacity-building workshops along with related materials.

Furthermore, the following sections detail InterQ's initiatives related to Open data [6] and ORDP [1], which enables open, online, and free access to research data generated by the project. The underlying objectives for this approach are as follows:

- Facilitate other researchers in building upon previous work or enhancing existing findings.
- Foster collaboration and prevent duplicate efforts.
- Accelerate the pace of innovation.

Figure 1 Open access to Research Data

¹ OECD, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, <https://www.oecd.org/>

2.1 Data Lifecycle and Data Protection Processes

A plethora of data were essential for realizing InterQ vision and objectives. These datasets encompass statistics, experimental results, simulations, and metadata derived from InterQ's testing and simulation activities. InterQ's data lifecycle can be summarized in four key stages, as detailed and illustrated below:

1. **Data Creation and Collection:** In this initial stage, data are generated or gathered by the respective owner and transferred to the relevant processor in a structured format. This format facilitates utilization by other partners or components.
2. **Data Processing and Analysis:** This stage involves actions aimed at ensuring that the data can meet the project's testing requirements. These actions encompass data verification, transformation, integration, and extraction, among others.
3. **Data Publication and Utilisation:** The step of data utilisation includes the actions toward data sharing, internally to the projects' consortium. At this stage, all processes need to be followed to ensure the integrity of the data as well as that they are shared with the appropriate protection for proprietary data.
4. **Data Storage, Archiving, and Reuse:** This stage pertains to data storage, archiving, and disposal to facilitate data reusability, aligning with the FAIR guidelines for data treatment. This step also includes measures to prevent accidental data loss or deletion, data corruption or even unauthorized access to the data.

Figure 2: InterQ Data Lifecycle

Due to the sensitivity of the commercial information involved in the project's pilots, it was necessary to assess whether the datasets from project end-users required aggregation or anonymization before handling or public release. To clarify these crucial concepts and the related processes, the following definitions are provided:

Personal Data: This refers to any information concerning an identified or identifiable natural person (referred to as the 'data subject'). Identifiability can occur directly or indirectly, such

as through a name, identification number, location data, online identifier, or specific factors related to the individual's identity. Information can be considered personal data if they can be linked to an identifiable person, even if accessed through a registry.

Sensitive Data: Sensitive data encompass special categories defined in Article 9 of the GDPR, including information about individuals' political opinions, as well as personal data related to criminal convictions or offenses. They also include private information to protect various interests in business, individual rights, organizations, research and development, politics, economics, and the security of the EU or its member states. Such data is considered classified and requires protection, typically being inaccessible to external parties without explicit permission.

Anonymization: Anonymization is the process of removing personal identifiers, both direct and indirect, that could lead to the identification of an individual. Direct identification may result from information like names, addresses, or unique personal characteristics, while indirect identification can occur when certain information is combined with other sources, such as place of work, job title, or salary. Once data is genuinely anonymized, rendering individuals unidentifiable, it falls outside the scope of the GDPR and becomes easier to use.

Pseudonymization: Pseudonymization is a data management and de-identification technique where personally identifiable information within a data record is replaced by artificial identifiers or pseudonyms. While pseudonymization can reduce the risk associated with data management and aid in compliance with data protection obligations, it does not achieve complete anonymization. There is always a possibility of re-identifying the party concerned through additional information. Unlike anonymization, pseudonymized data is still considered personal data under GDPR.

Metadata: Metadata refers to information about datasets stored in a repository or database template. For instance, metadata for an image may include details about its size, color depth, resolution, creation date, and other relevant data. In the case of a text document, metadata may contain information such as its length, author, creation date, and a brief summary of its content.

2.2 Open Access to Research Data and Scientific Publications

H2020 and in general publicly funded research and innovation projects aim to enhance various sectors within society, addressing environmental, economic, and societal needs. Open Access (OA) is defined as providing free and online access to reusable scientific information to other users. The advantages of open access to scientific outcomes are documented in detail in the "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020"² and are briefly presented below:

- Open information flow accelerates and streamlines the connection between market and innovation activities.
- Existing scientific publications and results that are accessible form the foundation for efficient peer-to-peer knowledge exchange, enhancing research quality, reducing effort, and eliminating duplication.

² European Commission, 2017: Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020, version 3.2.

- Ensuring transparency during research facilitates progress and the dissemination of ideas.

In terms of scientific publications, open access mandates that each beneficiary ensures free online access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications related to the results derived from project scientific research. InterQ's publications comply with these principles by providing free and online access to interested parties, wherein:

1. All articles or papers presenting the project's results are deposited on the project's website and Zenodo.
2. Every article or publication outlining the project's findings must include the following statement accompanied by the EU emblem: "The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 958357."

InterQ project and its partners recognize the benefits of open science and access to the project's results and innovations for the promotion and support of other research and industry partners at the European level. Furthermore, in this context, the four main principles governing project open data are summarized in the acronym FAIR, as explained below:

Figure 3: FAIR acronym

Findable: Data has a unique, persistent ID, located in a searchable resource, and documented with meaningful metadata.

Accessible: Data are readily and freely retrievable using common methods and protocols, metadata are accessible even if the data are not.

Interoperable: Data are presented in broadly recognized standard formats, vocabularies, and languages.

Re-useable: Data have clear licenses, and accurate meaningful metadata conforms to

relevant community standards, identifying its content and provenance.

2.3 InterQ File Repository Security Aspects

For the internal communication and coordination between InterQ project consortium members, all project files are stored in a Microsoft Teams file server. InterQ's Teams server is used to store and distribute internally all project-related documents, integrating also meetings and calendar services. It is a cloud hosted facility, providing an environment that operates using two-point verification security and world class data exchange, storage, and collaboration services. In addition, it uses Microsoft data servers, web/application servers, file servers and databases, where physical security is guaranteed by the service level agreement. As for the content security, access control is managed and fully configurable, while all users and participants of the shared documents server are provided with roles, and access rights. User authentication is used to provide access to the server data based on unique accounts. Lastly, it should be noted that all project information in the Teams server is

stored in a Microsoft Data Center located within the EU³. A screenshot of the Teams server is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 InterQ Teams Server Channels

Finally, information and datasets that was agreed to be made publicly available, such as public deliverables and project scientific publications were uploaded to InterQ’s Zenodo account, ensuring the sustainable archiving of them, see more details in Section 3.

2.4 GDPR and Other requirements

The imposition of the GDPR complements data-protection laws inside each member state of the European Union. GDPR rules are applicable to all those entities (e.g., companies, government agencies, non-profits organizations etc.) offering goods and services inside the EU or collect and analyse data of EU residents/citizens [5]. The primal objective of GDPR is to provide total control of personal data to their owners, while simplifying the related regulatory procedures inside the EU. In addition, another goal of GDPR is to give full accountability and information in case requested of the data owner regarding the processing of the provided personal data⁴ with the law. Due to its regulatory nature, GDPR has a direct application to all EU member states starting from the 25th of May 2018.

Figure 5 GDPR Layers of implication

³ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/privacy/eudb/eu-data-boundary-learn>

⁴ GDPR Article 4 define personal data as “any information relating to natural persons, that is or can be identified, even indirectly, by reference to any other information including a personal identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person. <https://gdpr.eu/eu-gdpr-personal-data/>

The above layers of implication for GDPR include a series of steps and activities that responsible institutions need to comply with, regarding GDPR conformity. Finally, the main roles and rules defined for parts for the GDPR implementation and compliancy:

- **Controller:** the person who determines the purposes and means of processing personal data o Obligations apply ensuring trust and cooperation with the data processor
- **Data Protection Officer (DPO):** Whenever required, following applicable GDPR and Member State respective legal requirements, the Controller and each Processor, may designate a data protection officer ("DPO") for assistance in monitoring internal compliance with GDPR.
- **Processor:** responsible for processing personal data on behalf of a controller o If required to maintain records of personal information and process them, will have legal liability in case of breach.
- **GDPR applies** to processing carried out by organizations operating within the EU and organizations outside EU offering goods/services to EU citizens.
- **GDPR does not apply** to any activities by the Law Enforcement Directive or for national security purposes or any activities carried out by individuals for personal use.

To ensure compliance with all the described data management directives and principles from the early project stages, InterQ established the following set of roles and responsibilities:

- **WP leaders** being responsible for adhering to the DMP guidelines and supervising their application in the work packages under their control.
- **The Project Manager of each organization** driving the DMP actions related the tasks and deliverables his/her organization is involved with, along with being accessible by the partner team in case of DMP-related issues.
- **Data Owners**, the ultimate responsible actors for ensuring compliance complying with the specifics of the InterQ Data Management plan, as well as the relevant GDPR policies.

For InterQ as a whole, Inlecom is responsible for monitoring and ensuring consortium compliance with the project's data management plan.

The Project Manager and the primary contact from each and every partner ensures that personnel working on the project have read the DMP and apply/exercise all the principles as described in the InterQ DMP (present document).

Finally, it is assumed that the collection of data from stakeholders in the project has been done in accordance with applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well will be processed and handled in a secure way and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection outlined above. Specific articles of the Grant Agreement (GA) mandate that all ethical principles comply to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct [3] [4]. In chapter 4, section 4 of the GA, Article 34 ETHICS AND RESEARCH INTEGRITY and Article 39 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA, dictate the roles and responsibilities of each consortium partner, since they are beneficiaries of the InterQ. Towards InterQ's objectives, the beneficiaries have full responsibility for implementing the action and complying with the provisions of the GA. Regarding compliance with Ethics principles, each beneficiary must submit to the coordinator in good time notifications for activities raising ethical issues.

3 InterQ Public File repositories

Open data repositories are online platforms that allow researchers to share and store research data in a standardized and accessible format. Open data sharing has many benefits, including enabling the replication and verification of research findings, facilitating collaboration among researchers, and accelerating the pace of scientific discovery. In addition, open data also promotes transparency and accountability in research, as it allows someone to verify and build upon the work of others.

Furthermore, repositories help manage and provide access to scientific outputs, such as publications, data, software and code among others, contributing also to the long-term preservation of digital assets. There are several open data repositories that are widely used in EU research projects, while access to the repository content refers to the general content of the repository and not to single access rights for specific records in the repository. This access can be:

- Open: external users can access the content of the repositories with no barriers
- Restricted: external users can overcome access barriers (e.g.: the repository requires authentication/authorisation to access the content)
- Closed: external users cannot overcome access barriers (e.g.: the repository content is only available to internal users managing the infrastructure)

According to InterQ's Grant Agreement, there is data that cannot be shared and had to remain confidential to the consortium for facilitating InterQ's partners business exploitation activities. Therefore, the data sets which are candidates for sharing, except for complying with InterQ's Data Management Plan, they also had to satisfy the following 3 criteria:

1. They were not confidential, i.e. they do not include personal or commercially sensitive information.
2. Sharing the data does not damage exploitation or IP protection prospects.
3. Permission from the relevant stakeholders and/or data subjects has been obtained.

The subsequent sections describe the Zenodo repository and a Git repository (e.g. GitHub or GitLab) where InterQ pushes its outputs and present how they are accessed by the public and how they comply with the FAIR guidelines.

3.1 Zenodo Repository and InterQ

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts. Zenodo repository was specifically designed to help researchers based in smaller institutions to share results in a wide variety of formats and across various subjects. It can be also used for the archival of workflows, taking benefits also from their integration with GitHub (<https://github.com/>). As Zenodo does not restrict the creation of communities by registered users, their creation and functioning respond only to the will of individuals and communities engaged with the repository.

Figure 6: DOIs for Research Data

As far as FAIR guidelines are concerned, ZENODO makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term. All uploads are enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number and Project Acronym. Zenodo provides version control and assigns Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) [7] to all uploaded elements facilitating the finding and re-use of data. Generally speaking, metadata will have a twofold nature: descriptive, therefore giving information on the data discovery and identification (titles, author, keywords) and administrative outlining when and how data was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it. Finally, metadata associated with each published data set in Zenodo will by default include the following fields:

- Digital Object Identifiers
- Version numbers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

3.1.1 InterQ Zenodo Community

All project publications shall be available to the public and the wider research community while adhering to the rules described at project’s Data Management and Communication and Dissemination plans, also ensuring the protection of project’s IP and business sensitive information. For this reason, InterQ project has created and maintained an account (i.e community) at Zenodo public file repository (see Figure 7) while all relevant uploads are linked to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) community for maximum findability. Lastly, all items uploaded to InterQ community in Zenodo are under the Creative Common licenses, meaning that everyone can re-use them with no restriction as long as they attribute the source of the information [8].

Figure 7 InterQ project community at Zenodo

The items deposited at InterQ Zenodo community will be retained for their lifetime, while Zenodo's lifetime is defined as 20 years (based on Zenodo General Policies⁵). It should be noted that non-confidential data are used to prepare public deliverables, publications, advertisement materials, etc., which are disseminated and communicated to specific stakeholder groups or Zenodo communities. Finally, through this action the project achieves sustainable archiving and knowledge management and abides with the principles of discoverability, accessibility and availability beyond the end of the project.

Table 1 InterQ Zenodo Community URLs

URL	Action
This link allows anyone to access InterQ Community in Zenodo and its collection of data.	https://zenodo.org/communities/h2020-interq/
This link enables the addition of a new record in the InterQ community collection. Uploads must be directly related to the H2020 InterQ project funded under grant agreement number ID: 958357.	https://zenodo.org/deposit/new?c=h2020-interq
A link to a OAI-PMH feed ⁶ , which can be used by other digital repositories to harvest this community.	https://zenodo.org/oai2d?verb=ListRecords&set=user-h2020-interq&metadataPrefix=oai_dc

3.1.2 InterQ and Git repositories

GitHub/GitLab are web-based platforms that allow developers to collaborate on and share software projects with others. They are based on the version control system Git, which allows users to keep track of changes made to their code over time and revert to previous

⁵Zenodo General Policies,

<https://about.zenodo.org/policies/#:::text=Retention%20period%3A%20items%20will%20be,next%2020%20years%20at%20least>

⁶ Open Archive Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

versions if necessary. Therefore, GitHub/GitLab play a significant role in the DMP of a project, especially when it comes to managing code and version control, which are crucial aspects of many research and software development projects. In more detail, GitHub/GitLab offer a range of features that make it easy for developers to work together such use:

1. Version Control: GitHub/GitLab provide robust version control capabilities ensuring that changes to project code and data are tracked over time. This is important for reproducibility and transparency.
2. Collaboration: GitHub/GitLab enable collaboration among project team members and collaborators can work on different aspects of the project while they track their contributions.
3. Documentation: GitHub/GitLab provide a platform for documenting code and data-related processes. A well-maintained README file in a Git repository can serve as a central hub for project documentation, explaining how data is collected, processed, and analysed. This helps meet the transparency and documentation requirements often expected in a DMP.
4. Issue Tracking: GitHub/GitLab users can create issues to track data-related challenges, questions, and improvements. This helps ensure that data management activities are organized and addressed in a systematic manner.
5. Automation: GitHub/GitLab support automation through workflows and integrations. Researchers can automate data-related tasks, such as data cleaning or validation, by setting up workflows.
6. Access Control: GitHub/GitLab allow fine-grained access control, enabling researchers to specify who can access and contribute to their code and data repositories. This aligns with data security and access restrictions outlined in the DMP, ensuring that sensitive data is protected.

GitHub/GitLab is widely used in the software development community and hosts a vast number of open-source projects that are freely available for anyone to use and contribute to. This makes it easy for other researchers to access and build upon these resources, improving the transparency and reproducibility of the research. Table 2 presents InterQ’s code repositories along with a short description for the code and their access policy.

Table 2 InterQ Consortium partners Repositories

Repository Link	Description	Access
https://gitlab.com/interq-h2020/ledger-api-server	The TF API	Open-source
https://gitlab.com/interq-h2020/chaincode	The InterQ TF Smart Contracts	Open-source
https://gitlab.com/eng-siena-ri/ten/ten-identities	The InterQ TF Identity Management System	Open-source
https://gitlab.com/eng-siena-ri/interq/personal-node	TF Personal Node sample distribution	Binary distribution, publicly

		accessible
https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/Erdre	Erdre: A machine learning pipeline for erroneous data repair	Open-source
https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/Udava/tree/master	UDAVA: Unsupervised learning for data validation	Open-source
https://gitlab.tekniker.es/aut/projects/9364-interq/geometricfingerprint	Source code for the geometric Fingerprint post-processing	Restricted
https://gitlab.tekniker.es/aut/Products/tms/	Source code for the data monitoring systems and Machine Axis Fingerprinnt	Restricted
https://github.com/nicolasj92/interq_cip_qhs	Learning factory TF adapter	Open-source
https://github.com/HannesJoern/interq_data_acquisition_public	Learning factory TF processing	Open-source
https://github.com/nicolasj92/interq_data_acquisition	Learning factory data acquisition	Open-source
https://github.com/bbc17/InterQ	Production Line Quality Prediction with Graph Neural Networks	Open source
https://gitlab.com/eng-siena-ri/interq/quality-hallmark-dashboard	Quality Hallmark Dashboards	Open-source
https://github.com/ejhusom/d2m	Data to Model (D2M)- A machine learning pipeline for trustworthy and green models, enabling	Open-source

	responsible AI	
https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/Eldre-Continual-Learning	Eldre for Continual Learning	Open-source
https://github.com/CFAA-EHU/broaching_wear_breakage_detection	Source code for broaching monitoring and anomaly detection (wear prediction and breackage detection)	Open-source
http://ceadaridg.ucd.ie:8000	Operator handwritten text OCR	Restricted

4 InterQ WPs Data Set Description

Chapter 4 presents project data set descriptions, their purposes, and how they're utilized throughout the project. In addition, the tables clarify the owner and source of the data sets used in the work packages along with their confidentiality status to ensure transparency and data security compliance. In line with the guidelines of InterQ DMP, the table provides essential details for each item used, such as:

- Description of the data set and it's format
- Data Owner
- Data Source
- Confidentially level
- Research purposes
- If applicable restrictions or requirements for using the data

This approach ensures both transparency and adherence to data security protocols across the project.

4.1 WP1 - Requirements Definition Data Sets

The aim of this work package was to establish the project's requirements, encompassing all essential aspects, including software, hardware (especially sensors), communication protocols, and standards, to achieve InterQ's objectives. Under this work package, various technologies for fulfilling project needs were evaluated as well as it was specified what and how to be develop, with a particular emphasis on meeting the end-users' requirements. In more detail the information collected and used by WP1 activities can be summarized in the following categories:

- Description of Pilots industrial parts, dummy parts, and quality control processes
- Production machine tool and data collection descriptions
- Process and Dummy process and data collection description
- Case studies and data flows description and relationships between UCs stakeholders
- Required sensor technology for project UCs

Table 3: InterQ WP1 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality
Industrial pilots' parts names, dimensions, material, batch size, annual production	InterQ Pilots partners	.docx, .pdf, .jpg, .bng	MS TEAM S	Y	Not applicable	Restricted to the consortium
Industrial pilots' parts inspections controls description and frequency	InterQ Pilots partners	.docx, .pdf, .jpg, .bng	MS TEAM S	Y	Not applicable	Restricted to the consortium

Information about Pilots including Models, Workspace size, CNC version, spindle power, tool holder type, operations and monitoring systems (physical, cloud, sensors)	InterQ Pilots partners	.docx, .pdf, .jpg, .bng	MS TEAM S	Y	Not applicable	Restricted to the consortium
Photos of Pilots processes phases and operations, including Typical lead time and description	InterQ Pilots partners	.docx, .pdf, .jpg, .bng	MS TEAM S	Y	Not applicable	Restricted to the consortium
Physical sensors/actuators, virtual sensors for Process control and product control IDs, and requirement for validation	InterQ Pilots partners and WP leaders	.docx, .pdf	MS TEAM S	Y	Not applicable	Restricted to the consortium

Upon careful examination of the data sets utilized in WP1, it has been determined that these data sets do not contain any personal information. The absence of personal information within the data sets ensures compliance with data protection regulations and minimizes any potential privacy concerns. Finally, all information provided by project end-users under this WP are accessible to consortium partners only, since they contain sensitive business information and proprietary knowledge.

4.2 WP2 – InterQ-Process Data Sets

WP2 work aims to enhance the quality control of manufacturing processes and equipment. To achieve this, there was implemented both physical and virtual sensors into the machine tool, enabling to evaluate critical process parameters and strengthen the Product-Data-Process quality standard. Under the activities of this WP, various datasets were compiled or produced, including:

- a) simulations to gain insights into the visual and tactile properties of different surface finishes,
- b) Broaching tests, gathering data from CNC machines, force sensors, and acceleration sensors to understand the applied forces.
- c) Fingerprint scans for identity verification purposes. Lastly, we closely monitored our machines and employed accelerometers to track their performance and vibrations

Finally, these datasets are indispensable for the success and continual enhancement of the InterQ project, while the nature of this information is business sensitive/confidential and therefore are restricted to the consortium partners.

Table 4: InterQ WP2 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions / Preconditions	Confidentiality
Surface finish simulations describing the topography of a surface finish ⁷	Matlab simulations	.png , .mat	MS TEAM S	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Broaching tests including internal CNC data, force and acceleration sensors readings ⁸	Broaching test bench	.mat	UPV server/ MS TEAM S	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Recorded data during the fingerprints	InterQ Pilots partners machines	.json, .mat, pdf	MS TEAM S	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Machine monitoring and accelerometers CNC data	InterQ Pilots partners machines	Database format (e.g. sbf)	MS TEAM S	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium

4.3 WP3 – InterQ-Product Data Sets

The WP3 goal was to develop quality sensors for product quality monitoring and develop digital twins for predicting the quality of the manufacturing products. The purpose of monitoring processes and errors detection, while the reliability, latency, and quality of the collected data is vital. These factors required the implementation of both physical sensors and models. In addition, the real-time transfer, processing, and analysis of data collected from different sensors took place. Table 5 presents the data sets collected along with their descriptions, while it should be noted that no personal data were collected in this WP, too.

⁷ The original data sets are restricted to consortium, but the test results might be public one day through a scientific publication.

⁸ The original data sets are restricted to consortium, but the test results might be public one day through a scientific publication.

Table 5: InterQ WP3 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions / Preconditions	Confidentiality
All files collect the same inspection variables. In particular, the decomposition of the impedance signal Vx and Vy over time during an inspection is presented.	Olympus omniscan Mx EC-equipment	.uff,.mat, .tdms	MS TEAMS	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Broaching teeth profiles	[BME]	CSV	MS TEAMS	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Broaching teeth trajectories	[BME]	CSV	MS TEAMS	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Cylindrical turning dataset where Each row describes the CNC parameters of a manufactured piece	Matlab Simulation	CSV file	MS TEAMS	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Topography images where each image depicts the produced part topography	Matlab Simulation	PNG file	MS TEAMS	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
Cutting edge pictures where the Picture of the cutting tool edge	Camera next to the cutting tool	JPG file	MS TEAMS	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium

Turbine Casing Surface Scan Multicolor images where the Dataset of images covering the whole cylindrical area of a turbine casing provided by CFAA/UPV ⁹	Images have been acquired by a vision system provided by VSYS	png file	MS TEAM S	Y	NA	Restricted to the consortium
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4.4 WP4 – InterQ-Data Data Sets

This InterQ primary objective is to derive indicators and data quality from sensor data collected during the manufacturing process across various use cases. These are based upon:

- in-motion data validation at the analog source of sensors attached to machine tools such as CNC machines
- historical data validation by temporal clustering of data from CNC machines
- repaired erroneous sensor data or virtual sensor data based on data from other operational sensors.

Time series data from various streams were employed towards this direction which includes both publicly available relevant data from Kaggle and data obtained from consortium industrial partners e.g. IDEKO, and use case stakeholders from the aerospace sector (ITP Aero/Aeromec), automotive industry (Renault), and energy sector (Gamesa). Finally, the information and data sets utilized under WP4 activities are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: InterQ WP4 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality
Bosch Production Line Performance:	https://www.kaggle.com/c/bosch-production-line-performance	CSV	Kaggle, ZENO	No	NA	Public

⁹ Images have been acquired by a vision system provided by VSYS, mounted on a 6-axis robot arm, programmed to scan almost the whole internal surface and the then the external one in a second arrangement. Note: for each scanned position (ie surface portion), 24 images have been acquired using different lighting conditions obtained by means of a programmable multi-color (RGB) and multi-sector (8) circular illuminator (annulus geometry); the goal is to extend the dataset and improve performance of defect recognition algorithms. Folder of each Scanned position is tagged by ROW (vertical height) index and a COLUMN one (angular position), while 0 to 23 index inside marks the different illumination conditions

Dataset used in the pre-study conducted as part of Task 5.4 for production line quality classification.	ch-production-line-performance		DO, MS TEAM S			
Broaching Single tool: Process variables form sensors and tool wear data gathered by automatic visual inspection.	Data from broaching machine using one cutting tool.	CSV	MS TEAM S	No	NA	Restrict ed to the consortiu m
Broaching multi tools: Data from broaching machine using three cutting tools. Process variables form sensors and tool wear data gathered by automatic visual inspection.	Data from broaching machine using three cutting tools. The broaching operation was to broach firtree slots on jet engine turbine discs.	CSV	MS TEAM S	No	NA	Restrict ed to the consortiu m
Bosch CNC Milling dataset: Vibration data from three milling cnc machines.	https://github.com/boschresearch/CNC_Machining	CSV	MS TEAM S	No	NA	Restrict ed to the consortiu m
Piston rod manufacturing dataset: Used for predicting remaining useful lifetime of tool.	Recorded during the machining process of piston rods at the center for Industrial Productivity learning factory.	H5	MS TEAM S	No	NA	Restrict ed to the consortiu m

4.5 WP5 – InterQ-ZeroDefect Data Set

InterQ-ZeroDefect WP main goal is to make manufacturing perfect without any defects. Data from the production process and products, collected and prepared in different stages were used. More specifically:

- Dataset used in the pre-study conducted as part of Task 5.4 for production line quality classification. The data sets used contained measurements of parts as they move through Bosch's production lines, with each part having a unique ID. The goal was to predict which parts will fail quality control.

- Data from the CNC and IC3 groups, contained timestamped process variables. These datasets were updated over time and used also in WP4 activities.
- Dataset recorded in the process learning factory CiP at the Institute for Production Management, Technology and Machine Tools, TU Darmstadt for the purpose of demonstrating and testing InterQ developed solutions. Analytical description of the data sets and the InterQ testing activities will be disseminated in public through an upcoming scientific publication at CiRP ICME conference.
- Data from the Real and commanded time series process variables recorded from a Nova 9 machine.

Table 7: InterQ WP5 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality
Bosch Production Line Performance	Kaggle ¹⁰	Csv	MS TEAMS, Zenodo	No	No	Public
CiP Discrete Manufacturing Dataset	PTW institute ¹¹	HDF5 format and CSV format	MS TEAMS, Zenodo	No	No	Public
Ideko Aeromec datasets	Data queried from the SAVVY API.	CSV	MS TEAMS	No	No	Restricted to the consortium
Fersa Nova 9 and Fersa 10 machines	FERSA	JSON	MS TEAMS	No	No	Restricted to the consortium
Datasets from multiple machines hosted on the Gamesa platform, Including process variables as well as a machine fingerprint	GAMESA Portal	CSV	MS TEAMS	No	No	Restricted to the consortium
Broaching Single and multi-tool	Data from broaching machine	CSV	MS TEAMS	No	No	Restricted to the consortium

¹⁰ <https://www.kaggle.com/c/bosch-production-line-performance>

¹¹ Hosted at the cloud of the PTW institute <http://cipdmd.ptw-darmstadt.de/>

Used for tool wear time series	using one cutting tool. The broaching operation was to broach fir tree slots on jet engine turbine discs					
CNC Milling dataset for tool wear detection	Kaggle ¹²	CSV	MS Team, Zenodo	No	No	Public
Renault dataset	Renault	CSV	MS TEAMS	No	No	Restricted to the consortium
Benteler Extrusion Detailing process variables from an aluminium extrusion process.	Acquired from benteler.	CSV	MS TEAMS	No	No	Restricted to the consortium

4.6 WP6 – InterQ-TrustedFramework Data Sets

The InterQ-TrustedFramework holds a pivotal position in data management, functioning as a dependable central repository for critical QA-related information components. These encompass identities, datasets used for quality indicator computations, and PPD quality hallmarks. The system assures backward traceability, safeguarding the immutability and indisputability of hallmarks while facilitating their traceability to the original data sets and the corresponding data source identities. This approach ensures the integrity of the hallmarks and their association with their data sources is maintained.

To enhance the security and transparency in processing of data, InterQ we rely on two complementary technologies: a blockchain network operated by INLECOM and a distributed database operated by TRIBUTECH. These systems work in tandem to safeguard registered identities and Quality Hallmarks, ensuring that the integrity and authenticity of our data are preserved while providing an immutable audit trail for our quality management processes. This combination of data sources and technologies forms the backbone of our robust supply chain and quality management infrastructure.

¹² <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shasun/tool-wear-detection-in-cnc-mill>

Table 8: InterQ WP6 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality
Identity descriptors of the active actors of supply chain / quality management processes (e.g., companies, departments, smart machines)	Process stakeholders (manual acquisition)	Blockchain records	InterQ Blockchain network	N	N/A	Restricted to the consortium
Documents containing a process-, product- or data-specific set of certified quality indicators (Quality Hallmark)	Output of quality assessment factory systems	Blockchain record, JSON document	InterQ Blockchain network and distributed database	N	N/A	Restricted to the consortium

In conclusion, it is important to note that within the scope of this Work Package, no personal information was collected or utilized as part of the research endeavours undertaken.

4.7 WP7 – Laboratory and Industrial Demonstrations

The WP7 objective was to demonstrate the benefits from the techniques and in general of InterQ framework e.g. I InterQ Trusted or Zero-Defect framework. Under WP7 a series of demos took place to validate the requirements set out in WP1 as well as measure the KPIs associated with project Use cases. Therefore, the information and data sets collected as part of all the previous WPs and WP7 activities are the same but used for different purposes.

4.8 WP8 – Exploitation, Communication and Dissemination Data Sets

WP8 focused on amplifying the influence of the project's technical innovations and outputs through targeting a various relevant audience. This included activities and initiatives to boost awareness and facilitate the practical application of project outcomes. Within this context, a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan has been meticulously crafted and implemented for engaging with stakeholders such as businesses, academia, and policymakers in various events that the project participated in. This plan served as a strategic roadmap for promoting the InterQ project, ensuring that its message reaches key audiences effectively. It also includes strategies for engaging with business leaders, academics, and policymakers, all of whom can play pivotal roles in improving or adopting project's outputs. Finally, InterQ project produced dedicated promotional materials highlighting InterQ's accomplishments and research results. Also, it should be noted that regarding the promotional materials where personal information have been included, explicit consent has been provided from the relevant participants and the participants have the option to opt out by project channels by informing the project coordinator or Inlecom.

Table 9: InterQ WP8 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality
Dissemination material from events e.g. Photo, images, video	Consortium partners (Retrieved during physical or virtual project events)	jpg, png, .asf, avi, mpeg	MS Teams, website	Yes	Explicit consent received from appearing participants, Lawful use-rights granted from media owners	Public
Scientific Publications/Papers	Respective paper Authors	pdf	MS Teams, Zenodo and Journal Websites	Yes (Authors details)	Gold open Access: Editorial websites	Public
Promotional material with general InterQ information e.g. Posters, flyers, etc	InterQ Grant Agreement and WPs reports	Pdf	MS Teams, Project Website	NO	Design agreed by Project consortium	Public
Generic project information Interviews with	InterQ Grant Agreement and WPs	Pdf	Website and social	Yes	Design agreed by Project	Public

partners Partner technology description	reports		media		consortium Contents agreed with involved partners.	
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4.9 WP9 – Project Management Data Sets

WP9 Project Management has collected diverse data for monitoring project activities and for fulfilling its documentation and reporting purposes. This dataset encompasses organization names, contact roles, email addresses, and phone numbers, along with details of their involvement in project tasks and responsibilities. Additionally, the project maintains a vital repository of official documentation, including the Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, and related Amendments. It also ensures that submitted deliverables, official logos, and templates for consistent project reporting and presentations are readily available to all partners through the project file repository.

To facilitate efficient communication and decision-making, InterQ tracks presentations, minutes, and agendas from WP leaders and General meetings. These materials foster collaboration and information sharing among consortium members.

Financial monitoring is upheld through interim financial reports, which detail the effort and costs incurred by each Consortium partner during evaluation periods.

For project management and oversight, Excel files are employed to monitor Gantt charts, deliverables, milestones, and project risks. These tools enable the project to remain on course and proactively address potential challenges. In summary, InterQ leverages these datasets and documents to promote collaboration, financial transparency, and the successful execution of the project. Finally, concerning files containing personal information of project consortium partners in the contact list, users have the option to opt out. By informing the project coordinator or ILS, their name can be removed from project lists.

Table 10: InterQ WP9 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality
InterQ Contact lists	Consortium partners	.xlsx	MS TEAMS	Y	Information published in this document must be updated by consortium members, as soon as there is any change of personnel involved in the project and their roles in their organisations.	Restricted to the consortium

InterQ Official documents	Consortium partners	.pdf, .jpg, .docx, .pptx	MS TEAMS	Y	Files can be exclusively uploaded by the Project Coordination Team	Restricted to the consortium
InterQ Meetings	WP leaders meetings and General meetings	.docx, .pptx, .mp4, .avi	MS TEAMS	Y	Only access to the InterQ partners	Restricted to the consortium
Interim financial reports	Administrative and financial departments of each Consortium Partner	.xlsx	MS TEAMS	Y	Only access to the InterQ partners	Restricted to the consortium
Project Monitoring	WP leaders meetings, General meetings and Funding & tenders portal (CE)	.xlsx	MS TEAMS	Y	Only access to the InterQ partners	Restricted to the consortium
Project Risks	WP leaders meetings, General meetings and Funding & tenders portal		MS TEAMS	Y	Only access to the InterQ partners	Restricted to the consortium

4.10 InterQ Data Sets Compliance and validation

The following table presents the formal confirmation that each InterQ's WP data sets acquired and used followed the proper management and criteria set according to InterQ's initial Data management plan report D9.2.

Table 11 InterQ's Data Compliance

Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values	Compliance						
			WP 1	WP 2	WP 3	WP 4	WP 5	WP 6	WP 7
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	XLS, XML etc.	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available,	100% received 100% accessible	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

	non-corruption, whole percentage collected								
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	100% usable by intended beneficiary/ies	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Relation	Data follow a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Data Processing and Analysis									
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic	√	√	√	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper	Capability of data for transformation	√	√	√	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

	format(s) for processing	on (if needed)							
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated	√	√	√	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Data Storage, Archiving and Re-Use									
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Security (b)	Access control provided	Access control setup	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Security (c)	Server is considered as safe enough (TLS connection protocol)	At least TLS connection configuration	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

Finally, Annex II of the current report details InterQ's Global Data Protection Policy as documented under the previous release of this Deliverable D9.2. Even though InterQ did not use any direct personal data (in the form of data coming out or processed during its research activities), it recognised the need for having in place specific processes and related policies so that there is discipline on the usage/storage/retention/opt-out etc. of data collected or produced from project activities.

5 Conclusions

InterQ developed and maintained a DMP in accordance with the EC requirements and best practices. This DMP served as a data inventory, detailing the data collected, processed, and generated by the project. It underwent regular updates, especially to identify the use of personal information, prompting necessary actions.

Additionally, a section of this report summarizes the roles and responsibilities of consortium partners, as outlined in the initial version of the InterQ DMP (M6). This ensures the security of shared information and compliance with regulations like GDPR. This section also encompasses all practices that InterQ followed to meet these requirements, including consent forms and internal processes prepared by InterQ, such as anonymization.

The final version of the InterQ DMP confirms that no personal data were used in project WPs activities, and all commercially sensitive data from InterQ Pilots partners were restricted for use exclusively by consortium members.

The report also discusses our implementation of FAIR data management principles, ensuring data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. To fulfil these requirements, InterQ selected Zenodo as a public research repository. InterQ also offers access to project software and datasets through Zenodo and public Git repositories. Zenodo public research repository was chosen due to its reputation as one of the strongest, most supported, and advertised data repositories for project outcomes.

Finally, all publications and underlying public datasets are linked using persistent identifiers (DOI versioning) to enhance data discoverability.

References

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- [8] Creative Commons licenses (CC) BY-SA https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/Open_Content_-_A_Practical_Guide_to_Using_Creative_Commons_Licences/The_Creative_Commons_licencing_scheme [last access: Oct 2023]

Annex I: Data Management Report

5.1 DMP Roles, Responsibilities and Templates

Table 12 Data Set's documentation Template

#	Name	Data Description	Data Origin/Owner	Format	Storage	Personal or Sensitive Data	Restrictions/Preconditions	Confidentiality	Retention Period
Guidelines	Please insert the name of the file	Describe the data/metadata that are/foreseen to be collected in the project activities your organisation participates.	Describe the source from which the data/metadata come from.	Describe the format of the data.	Please describe where the data will be/are stored. E.g. Project File Repository, platform, Gitlab	[Y/N]	If applicable describe any measures/preconditions for data access and sharing e.g. anonymizing, encrypt etc	{Restricted to the consortium /Public}	Duration of stored data (until when they will be kept).
#									
#									

Accordingly, datasets will be reviewed by the *Data Owners* and must be approved before becoming candidates for contribution to the open research. Following in principle approval, InterQ will then make the dataset available through the InterQ user community and upload content to the existing relevant and suitable open access repositories. Where data must be embargoed towards IP protection or exploitation, a timeline for its release will be provided. The approval of the availability of data in an open approach will need to be sent to the project coordinator from the actual *Data Owners* via email. For this, a consent that the data can be distributed outside the consortium must be included in the approval email to the project coordinator. The following information should be included:

Table 13: Open Data Ownerships

Data Owner	Description of data	Data filenames and version	Consent to publish data outside the InterQ consortium
<i>Who is the data owner</i>	<i>What the data include</i>	<i>Filenames and depository position</i>	<i>[YES/NO]</i>

Annex II: InterQ GDPR Policy

The GDPR definitions apply, as set in the GDPR Article 4¹³. In addition, and towards the goal of particularizing and complementing the definitions of Article 4, the following terms are introduced. Policy Recipients are advised to consult both texts to formulate the applicable definitions each time.

“Personal data” means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person that is processed by any Project Partner and Policy Recipient during execution of the Project.

“Controller” means the owner of the data (usually the creator of the data itself), unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.

“Processor” means each Project Partner, unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.

“Consent” of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous and in writing indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.

“Supervisory authority” means the competent Data Protection Authorities within the Project Partners' jurisdictions.

5.2 Policy scope

The Controller determines in advance what is the law applicable to the processing of personal data in a particular case, considering that according to EU law such determination comes from legal principles and cannot be derogated by the parties.

5.2.1 Establishment

Each Project Partner is established on the territory of EU Member States. In the event of any change in establishment, the respective Project Partner shall notify the Project Coordinator duly and in writing.

Unless otherwise expressly specified, each Project Partner is considered the controller in that Member State.

Processor outside the EU

In the event of any subcontracting to an organization not established on EU territory (such as subsidiaries pertaining to the same corporate group) that processes personal data of people staying on EU territory, on behalf of a Project Partner, that organization qualifies as Processor and ensures the fulfilment of the obligations imposed by the GDPR for that specific part of processing.

¹³ <http://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/article-4-definitions-GDPR.htm>

5.3 Personal data processing

5.3.1 Personal data

Personal data means any information relating to natural persons, that is or can be identified, even indirectly, by reference to any other information including a personal identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person.

5.3.1.1 *Special categories of data*

Special categories of personal data include data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation as well as the processing of genetic data and biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual.

In the event of such processing the Controller and/or Processor respectively comply with specific rules related to the processing of such data of special categories, as collecting specific informed consent from data subject and applying stricter safeguards.

When the Controller and/or Processor relies on data subject's consent as a legal ground for processing special categories of data, it will meet all legal consent requirements; otherwise, they are only processed if and to the extent it is based on one of the legal grounds listed in the GDPR for the processing of such data.

5.3.1.2 *Data anonymisation*

Whenever possible, including non-detrimental to Project execution purposes, Controller and Project Partners shall undertake efforts to keep personal data processed by them for Project purposes anonymous or pseudonymous.

According to the GDPR, "*anonymous information*" is information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. In this context, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.

Similarly, "*pseudonymisation*" means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

5.3.1.3 *Newsletters, social media and other dissemination material*

Unless otherwise expressly specified in Project contract, the Controller shall be responsible for the personal data processing carried out for Project dissemination purposes. To this end, the Controller shall:

- Collect and keep all relevant personal data (including lists of contact details), or copies thereof
- Monitor relevant communications
- Address to Project Partners instructions and guidelines on Project dissemination activities (including any EU or other state guidelines, whenever available)
- Inform Project Partners of any policy or legal requirements reviews and changes

5.3.2 Data subjects

5.3.2.1 Minors

Processing of children's personal data requires a special legitimate basis. In the event of such processing the Controller shall be informed in advance and in writing by Project Partners.

5.3.3 Data processing

Data processing means any operation, or set of operations, carried out with or without the help of electronic or automated means, concerning the collection, recording, organization, keeping, interrogation, elaboration, modification, selection, retrieval, comparison, utilization, interconnection, blocking, communication, dissemination, erasure and destruction of data whether the latter are contained or not in data bank.

5.3.4 Principles for legitimate processing

European Union data protection law set forth the following specific principles which must be complied with for the processing to be legitimate.

Pertinence and necessity - The Controller should implement management practices to fulfil the obligation to collect only relevant and necessary data for a specified purpose.

Purpose limitation - Personal data is collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes. The Controller has a clear overview of all purposes for which personal data is processed. Personal data is not processed for purposes besides the original purposes, unless the (secondary) use is compatible.

Data minimization - Personal data collected by the Controller must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are collected and further processed; if the same purposes can be realized in a less data intensive way a preference is given to that method.

Data update - Personal data is accurate, and, where necessary, kept up to date. Every reasonable step is taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased, or rectified without delay.

Data retention - Personal data is kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. The Controller and/or Processing concerned should have processes and policies in place to:

- (a) determine what the applicable (minimum and maximum) retention periods are for the personal data that is being processed
- (b) ensure that relevant retention periods are monitored

5.4 Data protection legal roles and responsibilities

With regards to the actors involved in personal data processing, the consortium was able to identify the following roles:

5.4.1 Controller

By determining the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, unless otherwise expressly specified in this Policy, the Controller is considered by law as the "Controller" and it is the primary target of the provisions of the law.

"Identification"

The data controller previously identifies itself as such and ensures an effective implementation of data protection measures to comply with the principle that personal data

are processed fairly and lawfully. The legal role of controller implies specific responsibilities because provisions setting conditions for lawful processing are essentially addressed to the controller.

“Accountability”

The GDPR provides full accountability of the company/controller regarding the compliance of its processing of personal data with the law. To ensure the effectiveness of that obligation, it prompts the Controller to follow an overall approach, achieving a genuine system of control and management of its pertinent information. So, accountability and compliance system are elements of the framework for the protection of personal data, in the cause/effect relationship: to be compliant and able to prove it (accountability), the Controller needs to put in place a comprehensive compliance system.

“Data Protection by design”

The Controller considers data protection issues from the outset and from the design of the Project, within the whole lifecycle of processing, to manage the issues in a proactive way, to reduce costs and improve efficiency.

“Data Protection by default”

The Controller standardizes data protection principles in personal data processing, products, and services. The measures adopted ensure that:

- Personal data is processed for purposes not different from the original purposes
- Only data necessary for these purposes are collected
- Data are not disclosed without human intervention

5.4.2 Joint controller

If at any time during Project execution the Controller processes personal data in conjunction with a third party, by jointly determining the purposes and means of the processing, they both act as joint controller. Both joint controllers determine the mutual responsibilities with a specific arrangement.

5.4.3 Processor

Unless otherwise specified expressly in this Policy, all InterQ partners handling personal data are considered as Data Processors, meaning that they process personal data under the control and guidance by the Data Controller.

A processor processes personal data on behalf of the Controller – that is, the Controller delegates all or part of the processing activities to them. In such event the Project contract assumes the role of the relevant required written agreement as per GDPR requirements.

The processor warrants that it shall provide sufficient guarantees to ensure compliance with the GDPR, has implemented appropriate controls to meet data protection requirements defined by the agreement, instructions and/or legal requirements and ensures the protection of the rights of data subjects.

5.4.3.1 Auditing

The Controller ensures the commitment of the Processor(s) to enable and contribute to any review activities, including inspections, carried out by the Controller or other (EU authorities’) auditors and/or reviewers, as appropriate.

5.4.3.2 Security

Each Project Partner undertakes that it adopts appropriate security measures to ensure the security, integrity and confidentiality of personal information and electronic communications

at an adequate level with regard to Project purposes, and at any event at no lower level than processing of similar data within its own organisation.

5.4.4 DPO

Whenever required, following applicable GDPR and Member State respective legal requirements, the Controller, and each Processor, may designate a Data Protection Officer ("DPO") for assistance in monitoring internal compliance with GDPR.

"Identification"

Each Processor appoints a DPO in accordance with the criteria and the requirements set forth in the GDPR, as applicable to it. In such event, it shall notify the Controller in writing accordingly.

"Designation compulsory vs voluntary"

Each Processor documents the reasons supporting the designation of the DPO or, rather, the reasons why such designation is deemed not necessary. This documentation forms part of the data protection documentation system of that Processor.

"Professional requirements"

The DPO has sufficient authority, professional qualities and independence to ensure success in his role, according to the GDPR provisions.

"Tasks"

The organization assigns to the DPO at least the tasks listed in the GDPR.

"Notification to Supervisory Authority"

Whenever a DPO is appointed the organization notifies the Supervisory Authority of such designation and publishes DPO's contact details.

5.4.5 People in charge of processing

Individuals who process personal data under the authority of the Controllers or Processor(s) must receive specific formal instructions. Hence, the Controller gives specific instructions, relating also to the implementation of security measures and safeguards, to all its personnel in charge of processing personal data.

5.4.5.1 *Training and awareness*

All Project Partners' employees should be well informed and aware of data protection implications and be able to carry out their obligations in their work. A data protection education and communication program should be in place and supported by a monitoring system that confirms all employees and/or contractors are appropriately trained on their data protection responsibilities.

5.4.5.2 *Policies and procedures*

Data protection policies and procedures exist, are documented in writing, are formally approved by management, implemented, reviewed, updated, and approved when there are changes to applicable laws and regulations.

All Project Partners understand, and the Controller may ask them to overview all their personal data processing, the data protection risks and the applicable rules and procedures. In such event, they shall provide it with all requested information to the best of their ability without undue delay.

5.5 Notice and consent

5.5.1 Notice

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, provides the information required by law to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, in particular for any information addressed specifically to a child.

The data protection notice informs data subjects about the processing of personal data relating to them, even when the personal data is not collected from them as well as of their rights, in order to let them verify in particular the accuracy of the data and the lawfulness of the processing.

5.5.2 Free and informed consent

Personal data is processed if and to the extent that the data subject has given valid consent to the processing for one or more specific purposes, or another legal basis for processing exists.

Systems or applications are able to document the explicit consent of the data subject so that it can be evidenced at any time.

Other legal grounds for a legitimate personal data processing are the following:

1. performance of a contract
2. legal obligation
3. vital interest of data subject
4. public interest
5. legitimate interest of the controller or third party

If "legitimate interest" is used as a basis, the interests that have preceded to the decision, need to be documented as well as any possible mitigating measures which will be taken to be able to proceed with personal data processing based on the defined interests.

5.5.3 Withdrawal of consent

Data subject's consent can be withdrawn at any time; even though it will not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

5.6 Rights of data subjects

The individual whom the data refers to (data subject) is entitled with specific rights set forth by the law. The GDPR requires that each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must facilitate the exercise of the data subject's rights, act on the request within a specific time frame and must communicate the information requested in an intelligible and easy to access form.

- Right of access

Any individual must be able to exercise the right of access to data relating to him which are being processed.

- Right to rectification

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request rectification of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases rectification is legitimate. If a data subject's request for rectification is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to erasure

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request erasure of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases erasure is legitimate. If a data subject's request for erasure is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to restriction of processing

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request restriction of processing of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases restriction is legitimate. If a data subject's request for restriction of processing is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to data portability

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, determines which processes are subject to the right of data portability as well as when the requirements for such right are met. Data subject can request the organization to receive a machine-readable copy of the personal data the organization holds about them and where possible, enable the transfer of this data to another data controller.

Portability right can be exercised when:

- (a) Processing operations are based on data subject's consent or on contract
- (b) Personal data concerns the data subject and are the same that the latter has provided to the organization
- (c) The right does not adversely affect rights and freedoms of others
- (d) The processing is carried out by automated means

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, implements appropriate measures and procedures to provide data subject, who is entitled to, with a structured, commonly used and machine-readable copy of the personal data it holds about him and where possible, to enable the transfer of this data to another data controller indicated by data subject.

- Right to object

Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, the data subjects have the right to object on grounds relating to their situation (unless the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest). The right to object is explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject at the latest at the time of the first communication with the data subject, presented clearly and separately from any other information. Measures should be in place to assess such objections and to ensure that such processing ceases when the request is legitimate and needs to be respected.

Data subjects have right to object, on request and free of charge, to the processing of personal data relating to them for purposes of direct marketing.

- Automated decision making

Data subject has the right to object to any automatic decision-making (including profiling).

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, will have determined which processes entail automated decision-making (including profiling) and will have established measures to allow data subjects to object to such automated decision making and profiling. Suitable measures are in place to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interest, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the Company/controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

- Timely response to exercise of rights

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must confirm to data subjects without delay whether data relating to them are processed and communicate the data to them in an intelligible form. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should implement internal procedures to be able to provide a timely response to the requests of data subject for the exercise of his rights.

Measures must be implemented in a way that effectively allows an individual to exercise his or her right to personal data, and that enables Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, to respond to such request appropriately within the required timeframes.

5.6.1.1 *Notification to recipients*

In case of a legitimate exercise of rights to rectification, erasure, or restriction of processing recipients of the personal data should be informed of the rectification, erasure of that data or of the restriction of processing.

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for communicating any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing to the recipients to whom the personal data has been disclosed and for disclosing these recipients to the data subject, if so requested.

5.7 Data protection documentation system

5.7.1 Register of processing

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, regarding their processing activities must set up a relevant record, maintained in writing (including in electronic form) and made available easily and swiftly to the supervisory authority on request, as per applicable legal requirements within their respective Member States. The record of processing activities shall contain all the information required by GDPR.

Consequently, the Controller shall have an up-to-date overview of all personal data processing activities and shall maintain records within the Project, that meet the legal requirements posed by the GDPR. By so doing, the Controller will be able to demonstrate compliance to any Supervisory Authority or other state or EU authority concerned.

For the avoidance of doubt, each Project Partner carries the same responsibility above within its own respective organisation.

5.7.2 Register of data breaches

A specific register where the breaches must be recorded together with other information specified by the law, must be maintained by the Controller and shown to the Supervisory Authority upon request. This register is an important element of the data protection documentation system.

Project Partners need to notify immediately and in writing the Controller of any personal data breach within their respective organisations that affects execution of the Project in any way, and to cooperate with the Controller while applying relevant GDPR legal requirements.

5.8 Data protection assessment

5.8.1 Assessment

If a Data Protection Impact Assessment (“DPIA”) is carried out under the Project, the Controller shall ensure that personal data receives the appropriate level of protection in accordance with the assessed data protection risk.

The decision whether to carry out a DPIA under the Project, unless undertaken in respective Project contract, will be made by the Controller upon prior written consultation with the Project Partners.

5.8.1.1 *Adequacy of protection*

The Controller, assisted by Project Partners, should have a process in place to assess for all processing the risks of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural

persons, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of personal data processing.

5.8.1.2 Impact assessment in case of high risk (DPIA)

When the preliminary assessment highlights that processing represents high risks, a formal and documented DPIA is carried out by ascertaining possible impact on data subject. DPIA is conducted in such a way to meet all the requirements set forth by the GDPR (art. 35) to confirm the quality and validity of the findings.

5.8.1.3 Prior consultation to Supervisory Authority

The Controller has a process in place and roles are assigned in order to ensure that when a DPIA determines that the processing represents high risks, the competent Supervisory Authority is consulted prior to the processing.

5.9 Technical and organizational measures

The Controller and each Project Partner, as appropriate, adopts appropriate technical and organisational measures regarding Project execution (the “**Measures**”), and reviews and updates them where necessary, to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is following GDPR.

Each Project Partner shall notify relevant Measures to the Controller in writing. In the event of any queries or further requests by the Controller, each Project Partner undertakes to address them duly and in writing.

If any Project Partner has notified the Measures to its competent Supervisory Authority, it shall inform the Controller thereof, and shall provide respective copies thereof.

5.10 Data breach

According to GDPR, the Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must implement adequate Measures to prevent personal data breaches.

In addition, the Measures should be able to minimize the adverse effects in case a security breach to personal data relating in any manner to the Project occurs anyhow.

Should a data breach occur, GDPR sets forth that the Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must notify it to the Supervisory Authority providing specific information, without undue delay and in any case no later than 72 hours from the time of knowledge.

When the breach leads to significant risk of serious adverse effects on the data subject(s) or serious adverse consequences for the protection of personal data, also the latter must be informed without undue delay.

5.11 Data transfers to third countries

No international transfers of personal data are expected to take place under the Project. In the event that any Project Partner wishes to carry out such personal data processing, it shall notify the Controller in writing and in advance. Unless otherwise expressly specified, any international data transfers carried out by any Project Partner for any reason during Project execution take place at its own exclusive liability and responsibility; same Project Partner shall hold all other Project Partners (including the Controller) harmless from any legal or other claims arising for such personal data processing.

5.12 Sanctions and damages

In case of violation of data protection principles and rules, each Project Partner (including the Controller) is responsible for damages and is subject to sanctions. Possible violations may involve civil liability and sanctions in order to ensure that any relevant damage is compensated.

The Project Partner (including the Controller) that is liable for said damages and/or sanctions shall hold all other Project Partners harmless from any claims, costs, and expenses arising from relevant GDPR infringement.

5.13 InterQ Web-server Personal Data Protection and Privacy policy

The following Personal Data Protection and Privacy Policy should be uploaded onto the Project Document Server (Microsoft Teams):

1. Introduction. This Personal Data Protection and Privacy Policy (the “Policy”) aims at providing details of the processing, and related methods of use, of personal data referred to users/visitors (the “User(s)”) of this website that can be reached at the address [<https://teams.microsoft.com/>] (the “Website”).

This Policy refers to EU Project [InterQ, 958357], (the “**Project**”).

Web users and visitors are recommended to carefully read this Privacy Policy before sending any personal information and/or filling in any electronic form posted on this website. This information is given in accordance with applicable EU data protection law, in particular the EU General Data Protection Regulation, and EU applicable Privacy law.

2. Controller. The Controller is the actual data owner per data set. Each InterQ partner introducing, transferring, or creating data for the needs of the project is expected to assume full ownership and responsibility of the respective data.

3. Scope. This Policy covers this web site only, and no other personal data processing under the Project or any other websites owned or run in any manner by the Controller or Project Partners.

4. Policy and information notice. This site has been designed with the main function of providing information on the activities of the Project. Therefore, in most cases, the collection of the user's personal data is not required.

In certain instances, such as the "newsletter" section and to allow the transmission of our newsletter, the interested user is required to fill out a data collection form. In these cases, the user is always free to provide his/her own data and consent to relevant processing. We recommend reading this Policy before providing the data.

In addition, should it be necessary in limited cases to collect personal information for other purposes, this will be clearly shown in the information privacy notices required by law, in order to enable transparency and user awareness. Consent forms and other documentation will be used each time, as appropriate.

The above information aims to define limits and methods of personal data processing of each service, according to which the visitor can freely express his consent and eventually allow the collection of data and its subsequent use.

5. Traffic data. The computer systems and software procedures used to operate this website acquire, during their normal operation, some personal data whose transmission is implicit in the use of Internet communication protocols.

This category of data includes IP addresses, browser type, operating system, the domain name, and website addresses from which you are logged in or out, the information on pages visited by users within the site, the time of access, time period of user's staying on a single page, the internal path analysis and other parameters regarding the user's operating system and computer environment.

This technical / IT data is collected and used only in an aggregated and not immediately identifiable manner; they could be used to ascertain responsibility in case of hypothetical crimes against the site or upon public authorities' request.

6. Cookies. No cookies are used by this website.

7. Redirects to other websites. From this website, you can connect through special links to other websites of Project Partners within the Project, or of third parties as applicable each time. Controller hereby assumes no responsibility regarding the possible processing of personal data by third-party sites and in respect of the management of authentication credentials provided by third parties.

8. Purposes of processing and data retention. The processing of personal data is carried out mainly by using electronic procedures and media for the time strictly necessary to achieve the purposes for which the data were collected. The User, however, has the right to obtain the cancellation of his data for legitimate reasons.

9. Optional supply of personal information. The supply of personal data required from the User, unless otherwise noted, is optional, but in case of refusal it could be impossible to fulfill the request, or the related activity mentioned.

10. Place of personal data processing. Data processing related to web services of this website takes place, unless otherwise expressly stated, at Controller's establishment, which provides for the corresponding server management. Personal data are only handled by technical personnel of the Controller, specifically in charge of processing, or others charged with occasional maintenance operations. These persons have received specific instructions on the confidentiality of this data.

11. Scope of data flow and dissemination. The data may be used by Controller and/or Project Partners' employees, as persons in charge of processing, to whom appropriate operating instructions have been given, as well as by third parties who perform operating activities on behalf of them and who act as data processors, to fulfill contractual obligations about the Project. Personal data are not disseminated to unspecified recipients. Detailed information on the names of the data processors can be requested by writing to the project coordinator.

12. Data protection rights. Regarding the processing of personal data, User has the right, at any time, to obtain confirmation of whether the data exists and to have it communicated to him/her in an intelligible format. Users also have the right to know the content and the origin of the data, to check its accuracy or to ask that it be integrated, updated, or adjusted. Finally, Users have the right to ask that the data be deleted or made anonymous or to request the blocking of data processed in violation of the law; moreover, they may oppose the processing of the data for legitimate reasons. Requests should be addressed to the project coordinator.

13. Policy updating. The possible entry into force of new laws, as well as the evolution and updating of User services or developments in the Project could make it necessary to vary the method of processing of personal data. It is therefore possible that our policy may be modified over time and therefore we invite the visitor to periodically visit this page. To this end, the policy document highlights the date of last version.

5.14 InterQ Day-to-Day Data Usage and Related Processes

Even though InterQ does not use any direct personal data (in the form of data coming out or processed during its research activities), it recognises the needs for creating some process related policies so that there is overall agreement of the usage/storage/retention/opt-out etc. of data from every-day (day-to-day) project activities. A list of such matters is included below where the means that the consortium will tackle them reflects the whole consortium agreed approach.

5.14.1 Meetings' related material

This relates to any document created and used for the purposes of project meetings. These may relate to agendas, presentations, minutes, signature lists or any other internal document created for the purposes of InterQ meetings. All these documents will be created and maintained for internal purposes of InterQ and only InterQ partners will have access to them at the InterQ Microsoft Teams server under the meetings folder. They will be kept for 5 years after the project end (for auditing reasons, i.e. 31/10/2028). Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator before or after the meeting.

5.14.2 Workshops/Conferences and Training sessions

These data relate to the creation of workshops, agendas, programmes, participants' lists etc. and in general dissemination material related to InterQ-organised workshops. Regarding the external publication, we consider that this material can be fully anonymized so that it excludes personal information from the presenters/participants in the related programmes/agendas that will be shared publicly. For the parts of the related material that will be used for the workshop organisation internally to InterQ, the related files will be stored in the InterQ Microsoft Teams server under the folder meetings. The data will be kept for 5 years after the project end for auditing reasons (i.e., 30/5/2028). Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator before or after the event.

5.14.3 Reporting

Reporting refers to internal and external (EC) documents including InterQ progress of activities, technical overviews etc. Related files will be including documents (reports with no personal identifiable information) and financial data (C forms) sometimes including personal data. The purpose of these data is financial so that partners can claim budget requests for their related effort in InterQ. C forms will be maintained by the project coordinator only and stored at an internal and secure server. These (per partner) data are not to be shared with anyone internally or externally to InterQ, will be kept for 5 years after the project end (for audit purposes, i.e., 31/10/2028) and will be deleted after this date. Opting out of these data will be possible but will require an updated Form C to be submitted by the project partner.

5.14.4 Deliverables, internal documents and other InterQ reports

During the InterQ project, a large series of documentation and reporting will be developed relating to the project deliverables and/or internal documents etc. These files will be used for

the project contractual obligations and shared to: InterQ partners, EC, everyone (depending on deliverable type). In these documents, the name of authors will be included. Following this, as far as the internal (to InterQ) and EC distributed documents are related, they will be used only for the purposes of reporting and stored in the InterQ's Microsoft Teams server under the Project's Official Documents section. Reports that will be shared publicly (public deliverables) will mention only the partner name and not any other personal information. All reports will be kept for 5 years after the project end for auditing reasons (i.e., 31/10/2028).

5.14.5 Source codes

As far as the inclusion of personal information inside source codes is concerned, InterQ intends to not use any such information into actual source code files produced in the framework of InterQ foreground. In case that any partner wishes to include any personal information, a related consent form will have to be created, used, and signed by the data owner(s).

5.14.6 Usage of cookies (in InterQ sites)

In the cases that in an InterQ application (web) the usage of cookies is needed, a related pop-up window informing the user must be present, prompting the user to accept (or not) the conditions under which her/his personal information are stored. InterQ will maximize efforts to reduce the usage of cookies in its web developments.

5.14.7 Project related research data (data from demonstrations)

Any data circulated internally to InterQ for research purposes (i.e., data from demonstrations for source code analysis, sensor data for analytics etc.) must be fully anonymized by the data owner (in this case the data controller) and not relating in any case to personal information as stated in the sections above.

5.14.8 Any other InterQ related data

In case that personal information needs to be added in any other document in InterQ, the controller (document creator) will have to notify the data owners of their personal details being included into the related document, purpose, retention, storage etc.